

Salivary uric acid as a potential noninvasive biomarker for cardiometabolic risk

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Abstract

This study aimed to distinguish if there is a significant difference between salivary uric acid and serum uric acid when it comes to detecting cardiometabolic risk. The researchers seem to understand as to why salivary uric acid can be used as a noninvasive biomarker for cardiometabolic risk. One of the factors that interest the researchers in doing this study is that obesity is prevalent not only in the Philippines but in other countries as well. The study is experimental research whereas, it elaborates the methods that were used during experimentation. This includes the design of the research, the procedure of the study, instruments that were used, data gathering, flow chart, and the treatment of data. The research used an experimental-comparative design where the researchers found the cause, reason, and the pre-existing differences in the study.

Keywords: Biomarker; Cardiometabolic risk; Effectiveness; Non-invasive; Obesity; Saliva; Serum; Significant difference; Uric acid.

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Introduction

The salivary glands secrete saliva in the mouth, which is a slightly alkaline secretion comprising water, mucin, protein, salts, and usually a starch-splitting enzyme (Baliga et al., 2013). Recently, the use of saliva provides a better insight as an investigative tool for disease process and disorder diagnostic. Zhang et al. (2013) said that using the whole saliva is the top choice for diagnosis of systematic diseases since it is readily collected and also contains serum constituents. It is also useful for the investigation of pathology of the major salivary glands since it holds gland-specific saliva. Using saliva as an analyte may be applicable for diagnosis of hereditary disorders, autoimmune diseases, malignant and infectious disease and endocrine disorders, as well in the evaluation of medicinal levels of drugs (Zhang et al., 2013). The utilization of saliva is gaining popularity because of its distinct advantages over serum.

Purines produce uric acid as their byproduct (Kielstein et al., 2020). Purines are naturally present in the body as well as in various foods and beverages. The majority of uric acid dissolves in the blood and is carried to the kidneys. After that, it excretes in the urine. Certain uric acid-related disorders can develop if the body produces too much or fails to eliminate enough uric acid (Dugdale, 2021).

Approaches for salivary diagnostic testing have been developed to monitor oral conditions such periodontal disease and to estimate the risk of caries (Spielmann & Wong, 2014). A large number of medically important analytes in saliva are recently being gradually revealed through the use of emerging biotechnologies and salivary diagnostics, and some of them serve as biomarkers for various diseases such as cancer, autoimmune diseases, viral diseases, bacterial diseases, cardiovascular diseases, and human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) (Zhang et al., 2012; Lee & Kwak, 2014).

Because it may be gathered non-invasively, saliva or oral fluid has long been considered a viable alternative to blood and other body fluids for illness diagnosis and medication monitoring. However, due to a lack of well-defined salivary biomarkers for particular diseases, acceptable technologies for low sample volume analysis, and societal and professional acceptance, saliva diagnostics are not commonly applied (Yeh et al., 2010; Yap et al., 2020).

Diseases such as gout, kidney stones, hyperuricemia, obesity, hypertension, and metabolic syndrome exhibit an increase in uric acid as an indicator. Some studies have seen that there is a linear relationship between uric acid levels in serum and saliva, in this sense saliva analysis may be a useful as non-invasive approach for monitoring patients with cardiometabolic risk. In line with this, the most abundant antioxidant in blood, uric acid, reduces the physiological stress caused by free radicals on the body, preventing an ailment known as oxidative stress (Goodman et al., 2016; Soukup et al., 2012).

A metabolic syndrome is a group of cardiometabolic risk factors linked with the increased risk of cancer, cardiovascular disease, and multiple chronic diseases. In addition, due to the rise of obesity among adults, cardiometabolic risk is becoming more common.

Subsequently, cardiometabolic risk will surpass smoking as the leading factor for heart disease. Cardiometabolic risk increases the chance of having diabetes, heart disease, or stroke.

Saliva has protein, enzymes, hormones, and deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA). A recently discovered sample that can be used to measure hormone levels is saliva, including estrogen (estradiol), progesterone, testosterone, dehydroepiandrosterone (DHEA), and cortisol that can detect many factors that can cause a disease and other serious illnesses that leave a trace in the patient's saliva.

An increase in serum uric acid may indicate a lot of diseases, most common of which is gout. Other diseases that may contribute to this is the metabolic syndrome, this syndrome may cause a cardiometabolic risk. In this study, the use of salivary uric acid (SUA) will be determined as a form of the potential non-invasive biomarker for cardiometabolic risks. In addition, an increase in uric acid levels may also indicate cardiovascular diseases.

The researchers aim to determine if the salivary uric acid (SUA) is increased in patients with cardiometabolic risk and to investigate the relationship between salivary uric acid and cardiometabolic risk factors. The researchers decided to use saliva as a substitute for serum in detecting uric acid for cardiometabolic risk. Since it will use saliva as a specimen, the method is noninvasive to consider religions that do not allow invasive methods and to lessen the biochemical waste from using syringes when testing.

The group of researchers decided to focus on the use of saliva as a substitute for serum in detecting uric acid, which is used as a non-invasive biomarker of cardiometabolic risks. Different concentration of saliva and serum will also be discussed in the study for the future use of the researchers.

Objective of the Study

This study aimed to distinguish the significant difference of serum uric acid and salivary uric acid and the effectiveness of salivary uric acid as a potential non-invasive biomarker for cardiometabolic risk. At the end of the study, the researchers are expected to test the saliva of patients who are known to have elevated uric acid, identify the reaction of uric acid in saliva, and determine the limitations of using the saliva as a specimen in detecting uric acid.

Statement of the Problem

The study aimed to seek the effectiveness of salivary uric acid (SUA) as a potential non-invasive biomarker for cardiometabolic risk. Specifically, it sought to answer the following:

1. What is the level of uric acid in the saliva using enzymatic method?
2. Is there a significant difference in the level of uric acid in saliva and serum using enzymatic method?
3. Is the salivary uric acid effective as a potential non-invasive biomarker for cardiometabolic risk?

Scope and Limitation

This study focused on the test subject with known and unknown presence of increase uric acid level and obesity. The researchers conducted this study at the Animal Testing Laboratory. Testing utilized the enzymatic testing to determine if there is no significant difference between the serum uric acid and salivary uric acid. Further test shall be implemented after each result.

Methodology

Research Design

One of the most important steps in the process of making research is selecting the right research design for your study. It is compared to a blueprint for making many and different infrastructures. With these, the researchers have to be very careful in choosing the right research design.

The definition stated that investigators must have plan, structure, and strategy. The plan, it is an outline created by the combination of ideas from researchers to work on. The structure, it serves as the bone of the study. And lastly, the strategy used by the investigators to carry the power out of themselves to be able to provide enough information and solutions.

The type of research that was used in this research is experimental-comparison design. Comparative research is a study in which the researchers will find the cause, reason, and pre-existing differences in the conducted study.

Materials and Methods

I. Materials

A total of two clinical trials was used for this research. Each trial consisted of six obese rabbits. The researchers decided to use rabbits as subject since it produces more saliva and is sensitive compared to other test animals. Materials like, spectrophotometer, micropipette, centrifuge and test tubes were provided by the Animal House Research Laboratory. Reagents were bought from the manufacturer. Other materials like sterile container and reagents were bought from medical suppliers.

II. Preparation of Rabbits

A total of 15 rabbits in two clinical trials were used as a test animal since the concentration of their saliva is similar to that of humans. The researchers fed the rabbits with greater amount food to achieve the desirable obese body of the rabbits. Obese rabbits were the target of the researchers to test for the detection salivary uric acid.

A. Temperature

The temperature was at room temperature (25°C-27°C) to avoid any interference in the lifestyle of the rabbits. Since rabbits are sensitive in cold and hot weather.

B. Collection

A total of 1 ml of saliva and 2 ml of serum were collected from each test animal. After collection, the sample was refrigerated within thirty minutes, and froze at or below -20°C within four hours to avoid any false interference in the samples.

III. Method

The method that was used to determine whether salivary uric acid can be used as a potential non-invasive biomarker is the enzymatic method.

A. Procedure

For maintaining sterility, avoid contamination of the following processes and maintaining a safety environment for both students and the subject that are to be used, medical technology students were required to wear a complete personal protective equipment (PPE) such as: sterile gloves, mask, and hair cap and laboratory gown.

a.) Saliva

The researchers were to follow the test procedure according to the insert of the enzymatic assay kit. The following were the procedures:

First, the researchers pre-warmed the uric acid reagents to 37°C for five (5) minutes. Then prepare the desired number of well needed for the test. The researchers used one (1) set of well in each trial. When the pre-warm was done, 10 µL of standard, control and sample were pipetted into the appropriate wells. 10 µL of uric acid sample diluent was placed into the first two (2) wells to serve as the blank. 190 µL of preheated Uric acid Reagent was added to each well simultaneously using a pipette. After preparing the plate, the adhesive cover that was provided with the kit was placed. The plate was mixed in a 37°C microplate shaker for 10 minutes at 500 rpm. The plate from the shaker was removed and left to sat out for 10 minutes at room temperature. When 10 minutes was over, the adhesive cover was removed, and the bottom plate was wiped off with a water-moistened lint-free cloth to dry. After that, the researchers read the plate immediately in a plate reader at 515nm or 520nm, and the test results were finally recorded.

b.) Serum

The researchers used serum as a confirmatory test for the presence of uric acid in saliva of the test animal. Researchers were to follow the test procedure according to the insert of the enzymatic assay kit. The following steps were:

The first thing the researchers did was to prepare all the materials needed. Since the reagent was ready to use, the test tubes were prepared was labelled with the desired labels. For the blank, 25 µL of water plus 1 mL of reagent were pipetted. For the standard, 25 µL plus 1mL of reagent was prepared. For the sample, 25 µL of serum plus 1mL of reagent was prepared. Repeat the procedure in samples depending on the number of samples used. As for the researchers, they used six (6) samples in each trial. The vortex was used to mix the samples and reagents equally. The tubes were incubated for five (5) minutes at 37°C or 10 minutes at 25°C. After incubation, the extinction was mixed and read against blank at 520nm. The test results were recorded after reading.

IV. Flowchart

Figure 1. Summary of procedure in detecting uric acid in saliva and serum

Statistical Analysis

This information was to gather, tabulate, and process manually with the aid of a computer to determine the precise interpretation of the results. The data was organized, compiled, and analyzed in the tables to make it simple to see how the data differed from one another. The researchers actually compared the variance, which is a crucial distinction to make, even though they used the T-test to determine whether the means differed significantly. This is interpreted in tabular form.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Test results of uric acid in saliva

Sample	Before 7 days		After 7 days		After 14 days	
	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 1	Trial 2
1	11.2	16.6	13.1	16.1	10.4	13.1
2	12.8	15.2	12.8	15.9	13.6	9.6
3	13.3	16.2	12.2	15.1	16.2	8.4

Table 1 shows the test results of salivary uric acid of the rabbits before making them obese. During the initial results, it shows an increase in Trial 2 than in Trial 1. The values have also increased after seven (7) days of the subjects being obese in comparison with trial 1. However, after 14 days of observation, there is a constant drop on the other two samples when tested in two trials compared to the first sample.

Table 2. Uric acid level in saliva

Sample	Trials	Before 7 days	After 7 days	After 14 days
Saliva	1	12.43	12.70	13.40
	2	16.00	15.70	10.37

Table 2 shows the summary of the results in trials 1 and 2. Levels of salivary uric acid were collected before the two weeks of experimentation and after two weeks.

Table 3. Test for significant difference after seven (7) days between serum and saliva

Treatment	Trial	p-value	Significance	Decision
Serum vs. Saliva	1	0.992	NS	Accepted
	2	0.431	NS	Accepted

Note. *Significant at .05 alpha level; NS=Not Significant

The table above shows the test for significant difference between serum and saliva after seven (7) days. For Trial 1, the computed p-value is 0.992 which is greater than .05 alpha level which means the difference is not significant hence null hypothesis is accepted or there is no significant difference. For Trial 2, the computed p-value is 0.431 which is greater than .05 alpha level which means the difference is not significant; hence null hypothesis is accepted or there is no significant difference.

This means that if there is no significant difference in the uric acid content between serum and saliva for both trials, then we can conclude that saliva can be an alternative way in extracting sample for uric acid test.

Table 4. Test for significant difference after 14 days between serum and saliva

Treatment	Trial	p-value	Significance	Decision
Serum vs. Saliva	1	0.568	NS	Accepted
	2	0.904	NS	Accepted

Note. *Significant at .05 alpha level; NS=Not Significant

The table above shows the test for significant difference between serum and saliva after 14 days. For Trial 1, the computed p-value is 0.992 which is greater than .05 alpha level which means the difference is not significant hence null hypothesis is accepted or there is no significant difference. For Trial 2, the computed p-value is 0.431 which is greater than .05 alpha level which means the difference is not significant hence null hypothesis is accepted or there is no significant difference.

This means that if there is no significant difference in the uric acid content between serum and saliva for both trials, then we can conclude that saliva can be an alternative way in extracting sample for uric acid test. After comparing the statistical results between serum and salivary uric acid, they did not show any significant difference. Serum uric acid is known to detect the risk in cardiovascular as the levels increases since the amount of uric acid that can be excreted in saliva is almost the same as the serum, therefore, salivary uric acid is an effective biomarker for cardiometabolic risk.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study is conducted to identify the uric acid in saliva as a potential noninvasive biomarker for cardiometabolic risk. The measurement of salivary uric acid levels was done in two trials within two weeks, recording the weight, levels of uric acid in both serum and saliva. Levels of salivary uric acid were collected before the two weeks of experimentation and after two weeks. To further support the result, trials one and two were done for confirmatory. No significant difference were seen among the serum and saliva; thus, it is concluded that the salivary uric acid can be an effective biomarker for cardiometabolic risk.

Based on the results of the study, there was an increase in the levels of salivary uric acid in the test subjects, which were obese rabbits that were used during the experimentation. As seen in the given results, serum uric acid and salivary uric acid showed a minimum difference in their levels making salivary uric acid an effective potential biomarker. To back the up the given results, a statistical analysis was done. It was shown that there is no significant difference between the levels of serum uric acid and salivary uric acid making salivary uric acid as an effective potential non-invasive biomarker for cardiometabolic risk.

Based on the findings of the study, the researchers recommend the use of larger test subjects for clinical trials. Future researchers may use another sample in detecting uric acid. The researchers also recommend the use of proper protocol to prevent contamination and alteration of results. An additional test for confirmatory of uric acid in detecting cardiometabolic risk is necessary in conducting research. Researchers may try other methods in detecting uric acid in saliva other than enzymatic method. They may make use of salivary uric acid in detecting other pathological diseases.

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